

Orchestrating Inter-DC Quality-Enabled VNFFG Services in Packet / Flexi-Grid Optical Networks

Silvia Fichera¹, Ricardo Martínez², Ramon Casellas², Barbara Martini³, Ricard Vilalta³, Raül Muñoz² and Piero Castoldi¹

(1) Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa (Italy)

(2) Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Barcelona (Spain)

(3) CNIT, Pisa (Italy)

1. INTRODUCTION

Network Services (NSs) to be supported over the upcoming 5G infrastructure are envisioned to be very heterogeneous demanding different network functions (NFs) such as Deep Packet Inspection, mobile Evolve Packet Core functions, etc. with various levels of QoS (in terms of bandwidth, latency, etc.). To this end, virtualization techniques as being defined by ETSI Network Function Virtualization (NFV) architecture provides an appealing framework and context where effectively deploying such NSs. Specifically, NFV virtualizes NFs over general-purpose servers hosted in datacenters (DCs). DCs may have different size (in terms of the equipped IT resources) which can be located at different geographical locations being inter-connected via a Wide Area Network (WAN) infrastructure. Those NFs to be deployed in DCs are commonly referred to as Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). In general, specific NSs may require that a number of VNFs deployed potentially in different DCs are sequenced to form the entire targeted service. The selection criteria to choose the DCs where the NS' VNFs are instantiated is diverse, mostly depending on the NS requirements and/or an adopted policy/strategy of the cloud/network operator. For the sake of completeness, such criteria may aim at selecting DCs which minimize the end-to-end latency of the demanded NSs, attain an efficient utilization of the cloud resources (e.g., load balancing), etc. The ordered set of VNFs and their connectivity constituting NSs is commonly termed as VNF Forwarding Graphs (VNFFG) [1].

Figure 1 depicts an example of a VNFFG request to be deployed encompassing the allocation of different VNFs (*VNF_{a..e}*) at different DCs (*DC_{1..2}*). For each VNFFG, as commented above, besides describing the set of ordered VNFs (herein a single VNF is considered to be deployed in a Virtual Machine (VM) instantiated in a DC's server), it is also specified the resource requirements for each VNF/VM (i.e., CPU, DISK and STORAGE) and the networking requirements (i.e., bandwidth in Bytes/s, *Bw* and maximum tolerated latency in ms, *L*) for the inter-DC connectivity. Herein, the inter-DC connections are provided via packet virtual links created over a Multi-Layer Network (MLN) combining both packet and flexi-grid optical switching technologies.

VNFFG definition: {{DC1, [VNFa, VNFb]}, {DC2, [VNFc]}, {DC3, [VNFd, VNFe]}, CPU, DISK, STORAGE, Bw, L}}

Fig. 1 Example of VNFFG request definition

This work describes the deployed and implemented architecture of a Cloud/Network Orchestrator for automatically and dynamically computing and deploying NSs as VNFFG instances. The Cloud/Network Orchestrator is composed of two main entities: the Allocator for processing VNFFG requests and DC resource allocation; and a Transport SDN (T-SDN) controller (based on a PCE Central Controller, PCECC [2][3]) to compute/configure MLN connections. In this regard, two different orchestration approaches (*no network info*, NNI and *abstracted network info*, ANI) are proposed. They differ from the amount of network resources information (i.e., topology and resources) disseminated by the T-SDN controller towards the Allocator. In the NNI, the Allocator only performs DC resource allocation delegating the inter-DC connectivity computation to the T-SDN controller. In the ANI, in addition to the DC resource allocation, the Allocator operates with partial network information at the packet level which allows computing inter-DC connections. Each approach relies on a different MLN path computation mechanism for computing packet inter-DC paths. The devised Cloud/Network Orchestrator and both approaches are experimentally validated and evaluated within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed in terms of blocking, setup delay and IT/network resource consumption

Part of this work has been submitted to the European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC) 2018, <https://www.ecoc2018.org/>, and at the time of writing the current work the ECOC paper is under revision.

2. NETWORK SERVICE ORCHESTRATION ARCHITECTURE IN MULTILAYER NETWORKS

Fig. 2 shows the two building blocks forming the Cloud/Network Orchestrator: the *Allocator* and the T-SDN controller. As mentioned above, the Allocator receives, computes and dynamically accommodates VNFFG requests (*req*). Each received *req* is specified with the requirements described in Fig. 1. Hence, the Allocator keeps track of all DC resources via the Cloud database (DB). By doing so, upon receiving a new *req* the Allocator checks whether it can be accommodated with regard to the Cloud/IT resources. The Allocator then interfaces the T-SDN controller (depending on the adopted approach, i.e., ANI or NNI) to request inter-DC path computations, to retrieve network information and to instantiate inter-DC connections.

The T-SDN Controller supports the following functions: processing packet connection requests from the Allocator (via a NBI API that uses the PCEP protocol), performing path computations, and configuring the computed packet and optical network elements (i.e., switches and Sliceable Bandwidth Variable Transceivers, SBVTs).

Fig. 2 Cloud/Network Orchestrator Architecture

Depending where the path computation is triggered according to the available network information, two algorithms are used. On the one hand, in the NNI, MLN path computation for the inter-DC connectivity is always tackled at the T-SDN controller using the information gathered in the Traffic Engineering Database (TED). Recall that in the NNI, the Allocator is unaware of the underlying WAN details. To do this, the considered mechanism relies on a modified Yen algorithm providing K-CSPF calculations. This path computation provides the shortest path cost satisfying the Bw requirement where both electrical and optical grooming opportunities are fostered. The K-CSPF algorithm sorts the computed k th MLN paths with respect to their total cost. Paths with the same cost are sorted by the lowest latency. The first resulting computed MLN path satisfying the latency restriction is chosen. On the other hand, in the ANI, the Allocator leverages the abstracted vision of existing virtual links (collected in TED*) and aims at reusing the spare bandwidth of the existing virtual links to compute inter-DC connections for the *req* as long as the Bw and L requirements are satisfied. This is done, applying a modified CSPF algorithm. If the Allocator is unable to find a feasible inter-DC connectivity, it delegates the path computation to the T-SDN controller which applies the k-CSPF algorithm described above.

3. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The experimental validation of the protocol interactions between the Allocator and the T-SDN controller of the whole system to dynamically and automatically serve a VNFFG request is carried out within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed. The deployed cloud/network infrastructure is shown in Fig. 2. Such an infrastructure is formed by different (emulated) DCs linked to 5 gateway (*Gw*) packet switching nodes. Each *Gw* node has a single packet port connected to the optical flexi-grid switch via an SBVT device. Optical links support accommodating flexi-grid optical connection flows and they have different fiber distances. The link distance of the fiber links is crucial when computing MLN paths (i.e., K-CSPF algorithm) not only for selecting the optical parameters of the SBVT (i.e. number of subtransponders and modulation format) but also to not exceeding the maximum delay requested by each particular NS request (VNFFG *req*).

Fig. 3: Workflows for VNFFG establishment: (left) NNI approach; (right) ANI approaches

Fig. 3 details the workflows (i.e., functions and exchanged control messages) to set up a received VNFFG *req*. Specifically, Fig. 3(left) deals with the NNI approach. If the *req* demands an amount of IT resources that cannot be satisfied (e.g., in a particular DC), the Allocator blocks the req. Otherwise, the Allocator decomposes the *req* in a set of packet inter-DC connections (*Pkt_LSPis*) to be set up. For a *req* involving N DCs, N-1 unidirectional *Pkt_LSPis* need to be established. To do this, the Allocator sends respective PCEP PCInitiate messages to the T-SDN controller. Each message carries the endpoints DCs' Gw nodes, the required bandwidth (Bw) and maximum latency (L). The T-SDN controller computes a MLN path using the TED information (updated via BGP-LS protocol running at every node's agent). If a *Pkt_LSPi* computation succeeds, this is established using extended PCEP control connection capabilities³. In the considered MLN, a computed path may combine new flexi-grid optical path segments and existing virtual links with sufficient spare capacity.

Once a *Pkt_LSPi* path is established, this is reported to the Allocator via a PCEP PCRpt message. If not, a PCEP PError is sent. Notice that a *req* is successfully completed when all *Pkt_LSPis* are established. Otherwise, the *req* is blocked releasing all allocated IT and network resources.

Fig. 2(right) addresses the workflow for serving a new VNFFG *req* for the ANI approach. After checking that the required IT resources can be allocated, the Allocator triggers the computation for each *Pkt_LSPi*. To this end, it first retrieves (via a TCP protocol) an updated view of the existing packet virtual links which are then stored in the Allocator's TED* repository (see Fig. 2). Next, for each *Pkt_LSPi* a CSPF algorithm based on Dijkstra is triggered aiming at fulfilling the demanded Bw and L requirements. If a feasible path is found, the *Pkt_LSPi* is instantiated sending a PCInitiate message to the T-SDN controller with the computed path (Explicit Route Object, ERO). Otherwise, the *Pkt_LSPi* path computation and its establishment is asked to the T-SDN controller likewise the NNI approach. As above, if all the *Pkt_LSPis* are set up, the *req* is successfully completed.

Source	Destination	Protocol	Info
ALLOCATOR	T-SDN	PCEP	Path Computation LSP Initiate (PCInitiate) ①
T-SDN	OPTICAL N8	PCEP	Path Computation LSP Initiate (PCInitiate)
T-SDN	OPTICAL N8	PCEP	Unknown Message (30).
T-SDN	OPTICAL N7	PCEP	Unknown Message (30).
T-SDN	OPTICAL N6	PCEP	Unknown Message (30).
T-SDN	OPTICAL N4	PCEP	Unknown Message (30).
OPTICAL N8	T-SDN	PCEP	Path Computation LSP State Report (PCRpt)
T-SDN	PACKET GW5	PCEP	Path Computation LSP Initiate (PCInitiate)
T-SDN	PACKET GW5	PCEP	Unknown Message (30).
T-SDN	PACKET GW2	PCEP	Unknown Message (30).
PACKET GW5	T-SDN	PCEP	Path Computation LSP State Report (PCRpt)
T-SDN	ALLOCATOR	PCEP	Path Computation LSP State Report (PCRpt) ④
ALLOCATOR	T-SDN	PCEP	Close

Fig. 4: PCEP messages setting up a new packet inter-DC LSP

Fig. 4. validates the proposed cloud/network orchestrator depicting the captured PCEP control messages exchanged among the Allocator, the T-SDN controller and the network nodes' agents when dynamically serving a VNFFG *req*. Particularly, it is shown the PCEP message sent by the Allocator to the T-SDN controller (step 1) requesting the computation and establishment of a particular *Pkt_LSPi* needed for deploying the targeted NS. In this example, the demanded *Pkt_LSPi* requires a server layer connectivity (i.e., optical flexi-grid connection) to be set up before which eventually is used to transport the *Pkt_LSPi*. Bearing this in mind, the T-SDN controller via specific PCEP messages (PCLabelUpd) communicates with the optical network nodes' agents for setting up the flexi-grid optical connection [3]. In the considered MLN domain, it is worth recalling that any optical path segment being deployed derives on a packet virtual link inheriting attributes from its underlying sever layer technology such as the bandwidth and latency (sum of the traversed fiber link distances). This then allows the system accommodating demanded and future packet LSPs (*Pkt_LSPi*) when serving VNFFG *req*. In fig. 4, we observe that step 3 is used by the T-SDN controller to configure in the correspondign packet Gws the

configuration for the Pkt_LSP_i being served once the connectivity between such packet switch nodes has been provided by the optical flexi-grid connection. Finally, step 4 is used to notify the Allocator from the T-SDN controller that the demanded Pkt_LSP_i required for VNFFG req being served has been successfully set up. Observe, that for a given VNFFG req , the above process may be repeated for each new Pkt_LSP_i to be configured.

4. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is funded Spanish Thematic Network ElasticNetworks (TEC2015-71932-REDT) and produced in collaboration within the context of the EU H2020 5G TRANSFORMER project (761536)

5. REFERENCES

- [1] M. Zeng, et. al., "Orchestrating Tree-Type VNF Forwarding Graphs in inter-DC Elastic Optical Networks", J. Lightwave Technol., Vol. 34, no. 14, p. 3330 (2016).
- [2] A. Farrel, Q. Zhao, Ed. "An Architecture for Use of PCE and the PCE Communication Protocol (PCEP) in a network with Central Control", IETF RFC8283, Dec. 2017.
- [3] R. Martínez et al "Experimental Evaluation of a PCE Transport SDN Controller for Dynamic Grooming in Packet over Flexi-Grid Optical Networks" ECOC2017.